

IMPLEMENTATION OF DISASTER RISK REDUCTION AND MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in the Context of Inclusive Education

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Abstract

Natural disasters and emergencies impose significant challenges on schools' capacity to maintain an inclusive educational environment, which contributes to inadequate protection of learners during and after disasters. The objective of this study was to determine the level of DRRM implementation and compliance in selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Schools Division Office of Rizal. It further sought to determine the significant difference in the level of DRRM implementation and compliance between schools implementing inclusive education programs and regular high schools. The study utilized a descriptive-inferential methodology. The data were collected using a researcher-made survey questionnaire anchored on the DepEd School DRRM Manual. One hundred thirty-eight (138) public secondary school teachers from Tanay Sub-Office participated in conduct of the study. The findings revealed that DRRM measures have been widely implemented in all four DRRM areas: prevention and mitigation, preparedness, response, and post-disaster recovery and rehabilitation. Schools were also found to be compliant with the Comprehensive Schools Safety pillars. Furthermore, the study found no significant difference in the level of DRRM implementation when participants are classified in terms of their school type. However, in terms of level of DRRM compliance, the study revealed that schools offering inclusive education programs had a higher level of DRRM compliance compared to regular high schools, particularly in School Disaster Management and Risk Reduction and Resilience Education. The study recommends that the Department of Education update its Comprehensive DRRM policy and support framework, ensuring they align with global standards. Future research should consider investigating factors that contribute to higher DRRM implementation and compliance in schools offering inclusive education programs.

Keywords: *disaster risk reduction management, inclusive education, natural disasters, policies*

Introduction

Globally, natural disasters and catastrophes present substantial obstacles to educational systems, resulting in physical destruction, diminished instructional hours, and psychological distress for students and staff, consequently compromising schools' capacity to provide inclusive education for all learners. Valeria et. al. (2020) state that disasters have the potential to undermine education by interrupting learning environments, affecting vulnerable groups, and emphasizing the importance of disaster risk mitigation education in order to alleviate these threats.

Over the past decade, disasters and calamities worldwide have become more frequent and severe. Thus, the integration of DRRM into education policies and programs has gained increasing attention from international DRRM researchers and policymakers (Ronoh et. al., 2017). The necessity for effective approaches in reducing and managing the risks associated with disasters such as inclusive DRRM calls for prioritizing the participation and empowerment of marginalized and vulnerable populations in disaster planning, implementation, and evaluation to ensure that all community members are adequately prepared and protected (Give2Asia, 2018).

Policymakers use existing international framework such as Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction and Sustainable Development Goals to support inclusive disaster risk management for marginalized and vulnerable populations (ESCAP, 2015). These frameworks put importance to the reduction of risk of disasters by mitigating vulnerability and constructing resilient infrastructure, while also ensuring inclusivity for individuals with special needs. Moreover, the UN acknowledges and reiterates the pressing need to reduce disaster risk by lowering the exposure and susceptibility of the marginalized population to disasters or by developing resilient infrastructure (DESA, n.d.).

Across Asia, numerous countries face the constant threat of disasters, both natural and human-caused, which significantly impede economic growth. Asia is very susceptible to climate change's escalating effects, such as severe storms, typhoons, and coastal flooding. The Asian Development Bank (2013) highlighted the region's escalating human cost of catastrophes as well as important DRRM policy challenges. This phenomenon presents new problems for disaster preparation, response, and recovery operations. Moreover, natural disasters pose significant risks in Southeast Asia, with countries like Indonesia, the Philippines, and Thailand facing high mortality, affected population, and economic damage risks (Nakasu et al., 2023).

In the Philippines, the government prioritizes disaster management and has allocated enough resources towards enhancing preparedness and minimizing the exposure and susceptibility of the general population (Alayna et al., 2016). According to the UNICEF, as cited by Punay (2018), around 5 million Filipino children with disabilities are susceptible to major calamities. Yet, current disaster preparedness efforts often fail to address their unique needs, leaving them further marginalized in times of crisis. This gap in inclusive education necessitates a closer look at how schools can be better equipped to ensure the safety and well-being of all students during disasters. Hence, continuing education and preparation for disaster management should be carried out on all levels.

In 2022, the World Risk Index, reported that the Philippines ranks 1st globally in terms of vulnerability due to the occurrence of disasters like typhoons, floods, landslides, and earthquakes. The risks from these hazards are further amplified by people's lack of awareness and insufficient information of these hazards. Furthermore, according to DepEd (n.d.), over the past decade, thousands of schools across the Philippines have been impacted by natural (43,810 schools) and human-induced disasters (29,949 schools). These events have resulted in widespread damage to infrastructure, disruptions to learning, and loss of valuable resources. While national policies like the Comprehensive DRRM Policy by DepEd (2015) aim to address these issues, the effectiveness of these policies ultimately hinges on successful implementation at the local level. This is where schools translate national guidelines into concrete actions. To gain a deeper understanding of how DRRM is operationalized in schools, focusing on a specific region or locality becomes crucial.

Therefore, focusing on regions like CALABARZON has become even more crucial as this region is susceptible to disasters such as earthquakes and other hazards due to its location and diverse landforms and topography (NEDA, 2017). Furthermore, according to Tilly et al. (n.d.), disasters in the region have led to significant damage and displacement of households, with a large percentage reporting partially destroyed homes. Hence, disaster risk reduction efforts in the region must prioritize educating and raising awareness among the local population about the potential hazards they face. Meanwhile, Tanay in Rizal province, is mostly prone to calamities such as flooding and other hazards (Pati & Cruz, 2017). As a response to this vulnerability, local government units in Tanay have been working on improving disaster preparedness and resilience in the area.

Within the framework of inclusive education, DRRM aims to ensure that schools are safe and resilient, and that learners and educators are endowed with the skills, knowledge, and capacities to effectively respond to disaster. DepEd has released a Comprehensive DRRM policy which aims to provide guidance for DRRM initiatives in the basic education sector, with the goal of enhancing resilience in offices and schools (DepEd, 2015).

In the context of inclusive education, learners require a unique approach to learning and understanding information, especially in times of disaster. However, during disasters, inclusive education can be disrupted because the unique needs and vulnerabilities of diverse learners may not be properly addressed in disaster response and recovery efforts. Serafica (2014) highlighted the lack of consideration given to individuals with special needs in evacuation centers across the country, primarily due to the non-compliance of the DepEd with building accessibility standards. Similarly, Stough and Kang (2015) emphasized the heightened vulnerability of learners with special needs in disasters, as schools often lack emergency management plans that cater to their needs.

Several obstacles contribute to the inadequate protection of marginalized populations during and after natural disasters, such as the absence of reliable data on individuals with special needs, lack of awareness of disability issues among governments and relief organizations, and physical inaccessibility of shelters and evacuation centers (Villamero, 2016). To address this, inclusive DRRM programs have been established to lessen the impact of catastrophes and increase their coping capabilities (Wester, 2017). Finally, schools must be knowledgeable about policies, structures, and practices in relation to climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction, and teaching during emergencies, as emphasized in School-Based Management Framework of DepEd.

While national policies exist, the effectiveness of DRRM implementation at the school level remains unclear. This study investigates the level of DRRM implementation and compliance in selected public schools within Tanay, Rizal. By examining the current practices and identifying potential gaps, this research aims to provide valuable insights for strengthening existing programs and developing targeted recommendations that can benefit a wider range of schools and ultimately promote inclusive education.

Research Questions

This study was undertaken to determine the level of DRRM implementation and compliance in selected public secondary schools. Specifically, it sought to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of DRRM implementation based on the Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education Framework in terms of:
 - 1.1. prevention and mitigation;
 - 1.2. preparedness;
 - 1.3. response; and
 - 1.4. recovery and rehabilitation?
2. What is the level of DRRM compliance based on the three (3) pillars of the Comprehensive School Safety (CSS) framework in terms of:
 - 2.1. safe learning facilities;
 - 2.2. school disaster management; and
 - 2.3. risk reduction and resilience education?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of DRRM implementation and compliance when respondents are classified according to the type of school?

Literature Review

UN (2015) and DepEd (2015) defined DRRM as the process and strategies to mitigate the impact of disasters. Its main goal is to produce a comprehensive and holistic strategy for disaster management that includes prevention, mitigation, readiness, response, and recovery initiatives.

Diaz-Vicario (2017), Paci-Green et al. (2020), and Thapa et al. (2013) stressed the importance of a comprehensive approach to school safety, encompassing physical safety, psychological well-being, disaster management, and emergency preparedness. However, while Paci-Green et al. (2020) mentioned that the majority of countries have implemented emergency management plans, Syahputri et al. (2022) found suboptimal outcomes in terms of teacher and education staff training as well as curricular integration.

Conde (2020), Mamon et al. (2017), and the Global Alliance for Disaster Risk Reduction and Resilience (2022) emphasized the need to integrate DRRM into school curricula and activities, involving all stakeholders in the educational community. These authors have highlighted the importance of incorporating DRRM into educational initiatives and engaging all members of the educational community to ensure a comprehensive and inclusive approach to disaster preparedness and risk reduction.

Boon et al. (2011) and DIDRRN (2018) highlighted that the expense of disasters disproportionately affects the poorest, most vulnerable, or fragile populations the hardest. These authors pointed out that these populations frequently have the most unfavorable disaster preparedness and may have fewer resources available to them, less access to disaster-prone locations, and less social cohesion. The statement implies that the author acknowledges the presence of discrimination towards susceptible groups within the framework of catastrophe risk reduction and management.

Studies by Wester (2017) and Johnson et al. (2014) revealed that disaster risk reduction is crucial for disasters to have less impact on people and communities. These authors stressed the importance of implementing inclusive and all-encompassing solutions in disaster risk reduction initiatives. In order to increase resilience and lessen the disproportionate impact of disasters on marginalized groups, they underlined the significance of addressing social, economic, and environmental vulnerabilities. They also emphasized the necessity of participatory strategies that provide the impacted communities with a voice in decision-making and give special consideration to their needs and viewpoints. These authors emphasized the value of inclusive disaster risk reduction in building more resilient and fair societies by bringing these factors to light.

Alayna et al. (2016), Garcia (2016), and Mamon (2017) acknowledged that there was a need for further research on the status and implementation of school DRRM programs, including the preparedness of teachers and students in dealing with natural disasters. These authors emphasized that a thorough awareness of the programs' present status and implementation is necessary for school DRRM programs to be effective. Garcia (2016) and others stressed the significance of undertaking additional study to evaluate teachers and students' preparation and preparedness for natural disasters. They stressed that this type of research will help educators and policymakers pinpoint the gaps, difficulties, and potential areas of growth in school DRRM initiatives. By highlighting these factors, the authors brought attention to the need for ongoing evaluation and improvement of schools' capacity to build resilience, assuring the safety and wellbeing of children and staff in times of crisis.

Ronoh et al. (2017) and Robas (2016) highlighted that there is a need to integrate DRRM into education policies and programs. Moreover, Gaates (2013) emphasizes the need for better disaster preparedness on the abilities of local governments and communities. They emphasize the importance of incorporating DRRM concepts, skills, and resources into the curriculum to raise student awareness and resilience. They also emphasize the importance of improving disaster preparedness at the local level by providing local governments and communities with the necessary knowledge and resources.

Garcia (2016) and Ecolin-Campilla (2016) found that most DRRM activities in schools are implemented. However, Mamon (2017) recommends that further research is needed to understand the preparedness of teachers and students for natural disasters, as well as their low-disaster risk perception.

Finally, SEAMEO (2015) and Thapa et al. (2013) suggest that inclusion can have important positive benefits for all students. These authors emphasize the idea that inclusive educational techniques foster the academic and social growth of children with a variety of abilities and a safe and stimulating learning environment for all kids. Schools and educational institutions can create equality, respect, and understanding among students through promoting inclusion, as well as a sense of belonging and acceptance for people with all backgrounds and talents. The study carried out by these researchers highlights the extensive benefits of inclusive education, emphasizing its ability to improve overall educational outcomes and contribute to a more inclusive and equitable society.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized quantitative research design employing both descriptive and inferential analysis. Particularly, descriptive analysis was used in describing or summarizing data points. Inferential statistics, on the other hand, was used to compare the differences between the sample populations.

Respondents

In the selection process, the researcher considered the respondents from regular schools and schools offering inclusive education programs. In total, there were six (6) public secondary schools that participated in the study. Two (2) of these schools were classified as schools implementing inclusive education programs while the remaining schools were classified as regular high schools. The respondents were comprised of 138 public secondary school teachers from Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal. Particularly, respondents were public school teachers teaching at either Junior High School or Senior High School. The researcher used pre-existing units such as school type as their clusters. These schools were randomly selected by the researcher based on the list of the schools provided by Schools Division of Rizal. A simple random sampling technique, on the other hand, was employed to target respondents.

Instruments

The researcher used a researcher-made instrumentation. The instrument was developed based on DepEd Order No. 37 s. 2015 which was elaborated through the DepEd School DRRM Manual. The author has made minor adjustments to optimize its relevance for the study's objectives. The questionnaire measured the level of DRRM implementation and implementation. It was validated by three (3) experts using the Survey Validation Rubric for Expert Panel by Marilyn K. Simon with input from Jacquelyn White. The first expert who validated the survey tool was the Assistant Chief of the DRRM Service of DepEd Central office. It was also validated by a University Professor with PhD in Education. Lastly, the tool underwent validation by a Registered Psychometrician. The survey instrument underwent reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha, with 30 participants' responses confirming its acceptable reliability, as determined by a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.990.

Procedure

The researcher sought data from SDO Rizal to identify the sample population and list of schools. After gathering preliminary data and obtaining clearance from the PUP - University Research Ethics Center, the researcher sought permission to conduct the study through the Planning and Research Unit. The researcher coordinated with the Public Schools District Supervisor, school principal, and research coordinator to gather respondents. The researcher ensured high confidentiality and privacy during the data gathering process.

Data Analysis

The researcher used certain statistical methods to help with the analysis and interpretation of the collected data. This study's statistical techniques included weighted means and the Mann Whitney U-test. Weighted mean is a statistical procedure which calculates the average by summing individual means of the weights. This statistical procedure was employed to determine the level of DRRM implementation and compliance. It helped the researcher with the decisions if some items are more important than others. In addition, the researcher employed a widely used nonparametric test, specifically designed to evaluate outcomes between two independent groups, in order to assess the means of two unrelated groups of samples. Particularly, Mann Whitney U-test was employed to determine the significant difference when participants are classified in terms of type of school. This is the appropriate method since the study deals with two independent samples that consists of ordinal data but not normally distributed (Taylor, 2023). The researcher analyzed the data was with the use of Microsoft Excel program and IBM SPSS 20. The alpha significance level of 0.05 is the benchmark score to accept or reject the null hypothesis.

The response mode to the Level of DRRM Implementation is arranged in numeric scales with the following interpretations:

Scale	Intervals	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Description
5	4.51-5.00	Highly Implemented (HI)	Strictly observed and implemented
4	3.51-4.50	Implemented (I)	Adequately observed and implemented
3	2.51-3.50	Sometimes Implemented (SI)	Sometimes observed and implemented
2	1.51-2.50	Moderately Implemented (MI)	Hardly observe and implemented
1	1.00-1.50	Not Implemented (NI)	Never observed and implemented

The response mode to the Level of DRRM compliance is arranged in numeric scales with the following interpretations:

Scale	Intervals	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Description
5	4.51-5.00	Highly Compliant (HC)	Strictly observe and complied
4	3.51-4.50	Compliant (C)	Adequately observed and complied
3	2.51-3.50	Sometimes Compliant (CI)	Sometimes observed and complied
2	1.51-2.50	Moderately Compliant (MC)	Hardly observed and complied
1	1.00-1.50	Not Compliant (NC)	Never observed and complied

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the findings, highlighting the essential findings and its implications.

Level of DRRM Implementation

The findings below highlight the functions of the school in the implementation of four DRRM areas.

Table 1. *Level of DRRM Implementation in Terms of Prevention and Mitigation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The school...		
1. conducts student-led school watching and hazard Mapping	4.46	Implemented
2. coordinates with the local government units in order to secure a copy of the community hazard maps	4.65	Highly Implemented
3. conducts regular building inspection including fire safety	4.49	Implemented
4. conducts risks analysis based on the profile of the school	4.51	Highly Implemented
5. identifies the natural and human-induced hazards that may be experienced by the school	4.61	Highly Implemented
6. incorporates results of student-led school watching and hazard mapping in the School DRRM Plan and School Improvement Plan (SIP)	4.61	Highly Implemented
Grand Mean	4.55	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented; 1.51-2.50 Moderately Implemented; 2.51-3.50 Sometimes Implemented; 3.51-4.50 Implemented; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Implemented

Table 1 shows the level of DRRM implementation at selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal in terms of Prevention and Mitigation. As shown in the table, it can be observed that 4 out of 6 indicators under this area were highly implemented. This area obtained a grand mean of 4.55 which implies a consistent and strong level of implementation. These findings aligned with the study conducted by Tizon and Comighud (2020), which also reported that the level of disaster prevention and mitigation was effectively implemented, as manifested by various indicators. Similarly, Ecolin-Campilla. (2016) found that the degree of DRRM practices of administrators in public elementary school in the Division of Pangasinan were rated as “Practiced”. However, Garcia (2019) found that there was a need for further research on the status of school DRRM programs, including the preparedness of teachers and students in dealing with natural disasters. This was further supported in the study of Mamon (2017), where learners were found to have a low perception of disaster awareness.

Moreover, indicator 2, which indicates that school excels in coordinating with the LGUs to secure a copy of the community hazard maps, garnered the highest rank with a weighted mean of 4.65. Domingo and Manejar (2018) highlighted that the local government plays an integral role before, during, and after disasters because they do not only have a direct jurisdiction over their constituents, but they are also expected to know the community’s needs as well. While the overall implementation is high, there may still be opportunities for improvement, particularly the indicator 1 which indicates school shall ensure that student-led school watching and hazard mapping are conducted, obtaining a weighted mean of 4.46. It is important to note that continuous improvement shall be sought to maintain a consistent level of implementation across all indicators.

Table 2. *Level of DRRM Implementation in Terms of Preparedness*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The school...		
1. Integrates DRRM in the School Improvement Plan	4.76	Highly Implemented
2. set up the School DRRM Team	4.84	Highly Implemented
3. ensures the establishment of an Early Warning System (i.e. bulletin board for weather advisories, bell/siren emergency signal and the like)	4.62	Highly Implemented
4. organizes training for DRRM coordinators, teachers, and school personnel	4.67	Highly Implemented
5. organizes orientations on School-based DRRM with prioritizing learners with specials needs	4.68	Highly Implemented
6. conducts information dissemination and advocacy campaign about DRRM	4.74	Highly Implemented
Grand Mean	4.72	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented; 1.51-2.50 Moderately Implemented; 2.51-3.50 Sometimes Implemented; 3.51-4.50 Implemented; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Implemented

Table 2 displays the level of DRRM implementation at selected public schools, based on the comprehensive DRRM in basic education framework, in terms of preparedness. As shown in the table above, the findings revealed a grand mean of 4.72 which signifying a high level of DRRM implementation. This is consistent with the study conducted by Baluran (2023), which found that in terms of preparedness, the level of DRRM implementation in one of the districts of Polomolok, South Cotabato is high. In order to create disaster-resilient communities and guarantee a secure learning environment for children, Widowati et al. (2021) further reaffirm that establishing resilience mechanisms that can improve school safety and fostering disaster preparedness starting in schools is crucial.

Moreover, it can be observed that indicator 2 which indicates that selected schools in the District of Tanay proved to have set up the School DRRM Team, got the highest rank obtaining a weighted mean of 4.84. Although all indicators show a high level of implementation, indicator 3 got the lowest rank with a weighted mean of 4.62 highlighting that schools should look into ensuring the creation of an Early Warning System which includes bulletin board for weather advisories and emergency signal such bells or sirens. This supports the claim of the Global Disaster Preparedness Center (2023) which noted that early warning systems reduce the risk that comes with disasters. It helps individuals, communities, and organizations reduce the potential effects of disasters by giving them advance information on potential risks and enabling them to take necessary action.

Table 3 displays the level of DRRM implementation at selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal in terms of disaster response. The data in the table indicates that the overall grand mean of the respondents across indicators is 4.68, indicating a high level of implementation. All twelve (12) items were rated to have “highly implemented” having weighted means ranging from 4.62–4.75. This implies that selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal have a great extent of implementation in

the area of disaster response. This supports the study conducted by Baluran (2023) where it was found that schools in the districts in Polomolok, South Cotabato have a high level of DRRM implementation in terms of disaster response.

Table 3. Level of DRRM Implementation in Terms of Response

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The school DRRM council/coordinator...		
1. ensures that all school personnel and learners are informed of the emergency situation.	4.70	Highly Implemented
2. serve as building marshals and check if all classrooms have been cleared during the evacuation.	4.65	Highly Implemented
3. coordinate with concerned government offices on any needed assistance for emergencies.	4.69	Highly Implemented
4. ensure that all advisers have accounted all their students during evacuation.	4.75	Highly Implemented
5. remind all advisers to conduct a debriefing session for students.	4.62	Highly Implemented
6. facilitate the debriefing session for teachers.	4.65	Highly Implemented
7. prepare the school for possible use as evacuation center.	4.67	Highly Implemented
8. assists the school establish temporary learning spaces, if necessary.	4.68	Highly Implemented
9. assists the school to facilitate the immediate resumption of classes.	4.66	Highly Implemented
10. provide immediate medical support, if necessary and within the school's capacity to do so.	4.72	Highly Implemented
11. assist the school head in collecting Rapid Assessment of Damages Report (RaDaR) 1 and 2 data.	4.68	Highly Implemented
12. communicate the needs of the school to external stakeholder.	4.68	Highly Implemented
Grand Mean:	4.68	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented; 1.51-2.50 Moderately Implemented; 2.51-3.50 Sometimes Implemented; 3.51-4.50 Implemented; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Implemented

Table 3 displays the level of DRRM implementation at selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal in terms of disaster response. The data in the table indicates that the overall grand mean of the respondents across indicators is 4.68, indicating a high level of implementation. All twelve (12) items were rated to have “highly implemented” having weighted means ranging from 4.62–4.75. This implies that selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal have a great extent of implementation in the area of disaster response. This supports the study conducted by Baluran (2023) where it was found that schools in the districts in Polomolok, South Cotabato have a high level of DRRM implementation in terms of disaster response.

Notably, the results revealed that the indicator 4 which indicates that schools ensure that all advisers have accounted for all their students during evacuation” has the highest rank garnering a weighted mean of 4.75. On the other hand, indicator 5 which indicates that the school shall remind all advisers to conduct a debriefing session for students as part of response measures, has the lowest rank obtaining a weighted mean of 4.62. This corroborates the claim of School Disaster Risk Management Guidelines for Southeast Asia where psychosocial support should be given as part of response measure (Resilience Library, 2016). They further highlighted that psychosocial support can be provided through professional counselling, psychological debriefing, and psychological first aid, which require proper training and knowledge in school settings. Overall, the grand mean of 4.68 suggests that the selected public schools have highly implemented response measures, demonstrating a strong commitment to addressing the immediate needs of the school community in the event of a disaster

Table 4. Level of DRRM Implementation in Terms of Recovery and Rehabilitation

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The school...		
1. provide assistance to affected learners by identifying and mobilizing funding program.	4.47	Implemented
2. rebuild/restore/repair affected buildings/infrastructure to be more resilient to hazard events (ensure safer school site).	4.46	Implemented
3. ensures the restoration essential services such as electricity, water, and communication.	4.57	Highly Implemented
4. provide assistance regarding physical and physiological rehabilitation of learners who suffered from the effects of disaster.	4.57	Highly Implemented
Grand Mean:	4.52	Highly Implemented

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Implemented; 1.51-2.50 Moderately Implemented; 2.51-3.50 Sometimes Implemented; 3.51-4.50 Implemented; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Implemented

The data in Table 4 indicates the level of DRRM implementation at selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal in terms of recovery and rehabilitation. The findings revealed a grand mean of 4.52 which indicates a high level of implementation under this thematic area.

Notably, indicator 1 which indicates that schools have implemented measures to identify and mobilize funding programs to assist affected learners, has the highest rank with a weighted mean score of 4.47. Similarly, the school has implemented measures to rebuild, restore, or repair affected buildings and infrastructure to make them more resilient to hazard events, aiming to ensure a safer school site. This indicator received a mean score of 4.46, signifying that schools adequately observe and implement the policy standards. On the other hand, indicators 3 and 4 received the lowest rank, signifying the importance for schools to prioritize the restoration of essential services and offer rehabilitation assistance. Both indicators obtained a mean score of 4.57. This is consistent with the results reported by Heinemann et al. (2020), who similarly emphasized that giving priority to rehabilitation assistance guarantees equitable access to education and enhancement of life quality for all students.

The grand mean of 4.52 suggests that the selected public schools have highly implemented recovery and rehabilitation measures, demonstrating a strong commitment to addressing the post-disaster needs of both infrastructure and individuals within the school community. Hadi (2019) also highlighted the need for a comprehensive and collaborative approach to post-disaster recovery, involving various stakeholders, and drawing upon lessons learned from previous experiences to ensure effective and efficient rehabilitation and reconstruction efforts. These findings underscore the schools' proactive approach to post-disaster recovery and rehabilitation, reflecting a comprehensive and well-implemented DRRM framework aimed at ensuring the safety and well-being of the school community in the aftermath of a disaster.

Level of DRRM Compliance

The findings below highlight to the role of the school in complying with the pillars of the Comprehensive School Safety.

Table 5. Level of DRRM Compliance in Terms of Safe Learning Facilities

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The school...		
1. conducts school buildings inventory.	4.62	Highly Compliant
2. conducts risk assessment with school buildings.	4.65	Highly Compliant
3. identifies number of unsafe school buildings.	4.70	Highly Compliant
4. has systems for monitoring and quality assurance of school building construction.	4.58	Highly Compliant
5. has allocated financial resources for completion of needed action to address unsafe school buildings within a specified period.	4.58	Highly Compliant
6. has undertaken appropriate action regarding unsafe school buildings (e.g. upgraded, retrofitted, non-usage, etc.).	4.63	Highly Compliant
7. conducts regular inspection and maintenance of facilities.	4.65	Highly Compliant
8. has undertaken regular repair of minor classroom (including facilities) damages.	4.63	Highly Compliant
9. has defined, documented, and assigned roles and responsibilities for maintenance.	4.64	Highly Compliant
10. have allotted budget for routine maintenance of school facilities for safety and to protect investments, with transparent monitoring oversight at the school level.	4.54	Highly Compliant
11. have identified those schools that are expected to be used as temporary evacuation centers for disasters.	4.59	Highly Compliant
12. are clear with the roles and functions of the school in camp management vis-à-vis the LGU and DSWD as per Joint Memorandum Circular No. 1, series of 2013 "Guidelines on Evacuation Center Coordination and Management" and RA 10821 "Children's Emergency Relief and Protection Act" and its corresponding IRR.	4.55	Highly Compliant
13. follows guidance and regulation on safe school site selection, resilient design, and resilient construction.	4.65	Highly Compliant
14. considers access and safety for people with disabilities when designing and constructing school facilities.	4.66	Highly Compliant
Grand Mean:	4.62	Highly Compliant

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Compliant; 1.51-2.50 Moderately Compliant; 2.51-3.50 Sometimes Implemented; 3.51-4.50 Compliant; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Compliant

Table 5 presents the findings on the extent of DRRM compliance at selected public schools based in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal in terms of Safe Learning Facilities. As shown in table above, it revealed a grand mean of 4.62 which signifies that schools are highly compliant with Safe Learning Facility measures.

Notably, all items under this pillar received a highly compliant score. These findings manifested DepEd's mandate on strengthening resilience in basic education. To ensure the uninterrupted progression of education following a catastrophic event, this pillar also comprises classrooms or temporary learning spaces (TLS). This aligns with the research carried out by Paci-Green et al. (2020), which demonstrates that the majority of advancements have been made in the integration of safe design techniques into the building of schools. The majority of responding nations have laws pertaining to school construction that include both safe design and safe construction. Similarly, In their study, Cubillas et al. (2022) found that the participants showed a high degree of awareness in creating a secure learning environment, indicating a strong understanding of the topic.

Moreover, the findings revealed that indicator 2 which indicates that schools are highly compliant in identifying the number of unsafe school buildings, has the highest rank, acquiring a grand mean of 4.70. According to Bernardy and Schmi (2018), establishing building security and emergency measures can provide a safe atmosphere for students to achieve their full academic potential. While schools are generally compliant with safe learning facilities, indicator 10, which signifies the necessity for schools to provide funds for regular maintenance of school infrastructure in order to ensure safety and safeguard investments, has the lowest ranking with a weighted average of 4.54. This indicator also emphasizes the importance of transparent monitoring and oversight at the school level.

Table 6 shows the level of DRRM compliance at selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal in terms of School Disaster Management. As shown in the table above, it gained a grand mean of 4.63 which signifies a high level of compliance. This corroborated the study conducted by Díaz-Vicario (2017), where it was discovered that the majority of educational institutions implement initiatives to enhance school disaster management and school safety.

Table 6. *Level of DRRM Compliance in Terms of School Disaster Management*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The school...		
1. has a Contingency Plan, i.e. Preparedness Plan turned into response actions when a disaster strikes.	4.75	Highly Compliant
2. has available, accessible, and adequate first aid kit in every instructional classroom.	4.61	Highly Compliant
3. has at least 2 necessary and functioning equipment, in case of a disaster (e.g. fire extinguisher, handheld/base radio, generator, etc.).	4.63	Highly Compliant
4. has pre-identified spaces for putting up Temporary Learning spaces/Shelters in the aftermath of a disaster.	4.48	Compliant
5. has ready resumption strategies and alternative delivery modes to ensure education continuity.	4.68	Highly Compliant
6. has ensured that students completed the Family Earthquake Preparedness Plan; and school has reported completion to DepEd DRRM at the Central Office.	4.52	Highly Compliant
7. has established a school personnel tracking system/protocol in the event of a disaster.	4.57	Highly Compliant
8. has trained personnel to administer first aid to students and personnel.	4.66	Highly Compliant
9. has psychosocial interventions for personnel and students.	4.60	Highly Compliant
10. has trained teachers and other personnel who could provide psychosocial support to students.	4.60	Highly Compliant
11. annually reviews the School DRRM Plan and SIP with DRRM integration.	4.65	Highly Compliant
12. conducts Brigada Eskwela to ensure school safety and preparedness measures are in place.	4.75	Highly Compliant
13. ensures that students, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders participated in Brigada Eskwela.	4.76	Highly Compliant
14. has established functional early warning system to inform students and personnel of hazards and emergencies (protocol, warning signs, devices, IEC), considering national and LGU warning systems and protocols.	4.63	Highly Compliant
15. ensures that students participate in drills.	4.73	Highly Compliant
16. has an evacuation plan and procedures.	4.78	Highly Compliant
17. has a student-family reunification plan that is clearly disseminated to students, teachers, and parents.	4.59	Highly Compliant
18. conducted regular hazard-specific drills (at least 3 hazards) with participation of stakeholders (BFP, Medic, LGUs, NGOs, community, PTA, alumni, and others).	4.62	Highly Compliant
19. ensures that School DRRM Team has received DRRM training from division or region or partners.	4.62	Highly Compliant
20. has conducted awareness and capacity building for families and learners.	4.64	Highly Compliant
21. participated in the different DRRM/Climate Change Adaptation (CCA)/ Emergency in Education (EiE) activities of the LGU.	4.60	Highly Compliant
22. has included the needs of pre-school and out-of-school children, children with disabilities in school disaster management.	4.51	Highly Compliant
Grand Mean:	4.63	Highly Compliant

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Compliant; 1.51-2.50 Moderately Compliant; 2.51-3.50 Sometimes Implemented; 3.51-4.50 Compliant; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Compliant

Notably, 21 out of 22 indicators under this pillar received “highly compliant” remarks. Indicator 16 which indicates that school possesses an evacuation plan and follows established protocols, indicator 13 which indicates that schools ensure that stakeholders participated in brigada eskwela, and indicator 1 which indicates that schools have a Contingency Plan were among the indicators which got the highest rank. Conversely, indicator 4 which denotes that schools designated areas in advance for the construction of temporary learning spaces or shelters following a catastrophe is the only indicator that receives a “compliant” remark garnering a weighted mean of 4.48. UNICEF (2011) states that the creation of temporary learning spaces ensures uninterrupted access to education.

While schools under this pillar are generally compliant with school disaster management, schools need to ensure that they have established Temporary Learning Spaces ensuring their suitability and equipping them with necessary resources. This is also in support of DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2021 which establishes the process for providing access to quality basic education services following disasters or emergencies

Table 7 shows the level of DRRM compliance at selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal in terms of Risk Reduction and Resilience Education. As shown in the table above, it garnered a grand mean score of 4.54 and a compliance level of “Highly Compliant.” This indicates that schools ensure that students and staff actively participate in various DRRM/CCA/ and Emergency in Education (EiE) activities. This corresponds to the study conducted by Villabon (2021), wherein schools meet disaster preparedness in Pillar 3: DRR in Education. Notably, indicator 3 which indicates that school ensures that learners actively participate in different DRRM/CCA/ and Emergency in Education (EiE) initiatives attained the highest rank with a weighted mean of 4.65.

Despite their high compliance with Risk Reduction and Resilience Education, it is still imperative to substantially enhance DRRM capability-building for educators and other school staff. This is in agreement with the results reported by Martinez et al. (n.d.), which suggest that with regard to community capacity building, school community members have a high level of knowledge regarding disasters but have little faith in the school's readiness or willingness to participate in capability-building initiatives of the SDRRM. Consequently, effectively disseminating risk information and maintaining confidence in community preparedness continue to be

obstacles.

Table 7. Level of DRRM Compliance in Terms of Risk Reduction and Resilience Education

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The school...		
1. has integrated key DRRM and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) concepts in the curriculum based on the National Curriculum Guide.	4.54	Highly Compliant
2. ensures that skills and competencies of students are assessed through measurable learning and risk reduction outcomes.	4.54	Highly Compliant
3. ensures that students actively participating in various DRRM/CCA/ and Emergency in Education (EiE) activities.	4.65	Highly Compliant
4. has a DRRM capacity-building plan for teachers and school personnel.	4.52	Highly Compliant
5. ensures that school personnel are trained on DRRM and/or CCA.	4.59	Highly Compliant
6. has available and accessible quality and up-to-date DRRM materials.	4.57	Highly Compliant
7. ensures the presence of DRRM corner, with updated IEC materials posted in it, in every classroom.	4.57	Highly Compliant
8. has available educational materials to meet the different needs of children of different ages, gender, and disabilities.	4.58	Highly Compliant
9. carries out monitoring and evaluation to assess sustainable implementation.	4.57	Highly Compliant
Grand Mean:	4.57	Highly Compliant

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Not Compliant; 1.51-2.50 Moderately Compliant; 2.51-3.50 Sometimes Implemented; 3.51-4.50 Compliant; and 4.51-5.00 Highly Compliant

Indicator 4, which had the lowest weighted mean score of any indicator in this category (4.52), emphasizes how important it is for schools to give top priority to providing the most recent DRRM and CCA best practices to those who are in charge of student safety. Training should be tailor-fitted to the schools' needs and context to effectively ensure the security of the whole school community. This is in consonance with Oro & Benavides' (2020) study where respondents felt that the most important lessons learnt from the school tragedy were capacity building initiatives that increased knowledge and abilities for dealing with disasters.

Significant Difference in the Level of DRRM implementation

The table below presents the difference in the level of DRRM implementation between schools implementing inclusive education programs and regular high schools.

Table 8. Significant Difference in the Level of DRRM Implementation

Indicator	Type of School	Mean Rank	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Prevention and Mitigation	Regular High School	65.88	0.35	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	School Implementing Inclusive Education Program	71.62			
Preparedness	Regular High School	64.85	0.164	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	School Implementing Inclusive Education Program	72.22			
Response	Regular High School	67.88	0.642	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	School Implementing Inclusive Education Program	70.45			
Recovery and Rehabilitation	Regular High School	66.73	0.486	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	School Implementing Inclusive Education Program	71.13			

Legend: If p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho

Table 8 displays the results of the Mann-Whitney U-Test, which aimed to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of DRRM implementation among respondents when classified according to their school type. The findings revealed that there is no statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis across all levels of DRRM implementation. This is indicated by the P Values of 0.35, 0.164, 0.642, and 0.486. This suggests that there is no significant difference in the level of DRRM implementation between schools offering inclusive education programs and regular schools.

Ronan et al. (2015) observed that there is a widespread lack of preparedness for disasters, with children and families being particularly susceptible. While the data show a tremendous increase in research over the last 15 years and mainly good results, significant problems persist. These obstacles include concerns about methodological rigor, long-term effectiveness, and implementation. According to Alcayna et al. (2016), the Philippines, is a leading regional actor in disaster risk management. However, the Philippines lacks a comprehensive understanding of resilience and disaster preparedness strategies, necessitating future research to map actors, analyze community perspectives, and investigate socio-ecological systems to better understand disaster risk preparedness and resilience.

Even so, the data revealed a consistent higher mean rank for schools implementing inclusive education programs across all four (4) DRRM thematic areas. This data suggests that schools implementing inclusive education programs attained a higher level of implementation compared to regular high schools. According to Suleymanov (2015), the implementation of inclusive education is

becoming more evident and receiving greater support and interest in the education systems of nearly all countries worldwide. This only suggests that inclusive education is becoming more evident and receiving greater attention within the education systems of most all countries in the world. However, as Haug (2017) asserts, no nation has managed to create an educational system that fully embodies the principles and objectives of inclusion, as outlined by many international organizations. This only indicates that there are still significant challenges and gaps in implementing inclusive education practices worldwide.

Nevertheless, it is crucial to note that although there may not be a noteworthy difference in DRRM implementation between the two types of schools, there may still be variations in the specific practices and strategies employed by each school to ensure preparedness for disasters and emergencies. In order to effectively implement a comprehensive approach to school safety, readiness (motivation and capacity) may be enhanced, according to research by Kingston et al. (2018), which suggests that readiness barriers must be actively addressed as part of a comprehensive strategy. Furthermore, Abayao (2020) underscores that disaster risk governance requires the use of methods that involve communities and scientists in the collective identification of hazards, assessment of risks, and development of systems that effectively manage and reduce risks. Further research may be needed to explore these variations and identify best practices for DRRM implementation in different types of schools.

Significant Difference in the Level of DRRM Compliance

The table below shows the difference in the level of DRRM compliance between schools implementing inclusive education programs and regular high schools.

Table 9. *Significant Difference in the Level of DRRM Compliance*

Indicator	Type of School	Mean Rank	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Safe Learning Facilities	Regular High School	63.34	0.09	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	School Implementing Inclusive Education Program	73.11			
School Disaster Management	Regular High School	60.06	0.005	Reject Ho	Significant
	School Implementing Inclusive Education Program	75.03			
	School Implementing Inclusive Education Program	75.03			
Risk Reduction and Resilience Education	Regular High School	62.04	0.044	Reject Ho	Significant
	School Implementing Inclusive Education Program	73.87			

As shown in Table 9, it appears that there is statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis for the School Disaster Management and Risk Reduction and Resilience Education pillars. This is indicated by the P Values of 0.005 and 0.044. In this context, the data provides evidence that there is a significant difference in School Disaster Management and Risk Reduction and Resilience Education when respondents are classified according to their school type, suggesting a significant difference in DRRM compliance between schools offering inclusive education programs and regular schools.

According to DepEd (n.d.), schools with inclusive education programs attained a higher level of DRRM implementation and compliance due to their need for comprehensive DRRM plans and strong community support. Furthermore, it can be noted that the higher level of DRRM implementation can be attributed to the strict adherence on the implementation of RA 10533, aimed at promoting inclusiveness, which includes programs addressing diverse needs of learners, including those with infirmities and difficult circumstances.

This was further supported by a study conducted by Dela Cruz and Ormilla (2022), where they discovered a significant correlation between the degree of disaster preparedness and the execution of DRRM in elementary schools. This correlation was found in terms of safe learning environments, school risk management, and incorporation of DRRM into curricula. Furthermore, in a study conducted by Díaz-Vicario (2017), it was discovered that the majority of educational institutions implement initiatives to enhance school safety.

On the other hand, it displayed that in Safe Learning Facilities, there is no significant difference between the groups of participants. This indicates that in terms of ensuring a safe learning environment, both regular high schools and schools offering inclusive education programs almost have the same degree compliance with Comprehensive School Safety.

In the study spearheaded by Lopez et. al. (2018), it showed that schools had a good degree of disaster preparedness compliance. Yet, several issues surfaced, including inadequate training resources and insufficient training for the school DRRM teams. In spite of these difficulties, educators and learners felt that public secondary schools are compliant with DRRM measures most of the time. A similar study conducted by Asio (2021) revealed that while the respondents answered moderately complied, they are generally aware of disasters. Notably, while schools are compliant with DRRM measures, they still face several challenges that need to be addressed for schools to be fully effective in mitigating the risk of disasters.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions can be drawn: Selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office, Division of Rizal showed high level of DRRM implementation. This is true to all four (4) DRRM areas, such as disaster prevention and mitigation,

preparedness, response, and post-disaster recovery and rehabilitation. It can be concluded that schools are well prepared for disasters and have effective response mechanisms in place. The high mean scores on each indicator indicate that schools have taken a comprehensive approach to DRRM. However, the findings revealed several aspects that need to be enhanced to effectively decrease the influence of disasters on schools.

Selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office showed high level of DRRM compliance with the Comprehensive Schools Safety pillars namely (1) Safe Learning Facilities, (2) School Disaster Management, and (3) Risk Reduction and Resilience Education. It can be concluded that schools are mostly adhering to the guidelines and standards set forth for each pillar. It proved that selected public schools are strictly and proactively ensuring safe building facilities by accounting for a number of unsafe school buildings and conducting risk assessments. Furthermore, the result of the study reflects a strong commitment by the selected public schools to ensure the protection and well-being of the school community in the event of a disaster. This is evident in the high level of implementation of measures related to emergency response, infrastructure resilience, and support for affected individuals. However, it can be observed that there are still room for improvement in some areas, particularly on allotting a fund for regular maintenance of school facilities, establishing a Temporary Learning Spaces, and capacitating teachers and school personnel.

The study found no significant difference in the level of DRRM implementation on four (4) thematic areas between regular high schools and schools implementing inclusive education programs. It can be concluded that regular schools and schools implementing inclusive education programs have the same level of DRRM implementation. Nevertheless, it is imperative to note that whilst there may not be a significant difference in DRRM implementation between the two types of schools, there may still be variations in the specific practices and strategies employed by each school to ensure preparedness for disasters and emergencies.

In terms of School Disaster Management and Risk Reduction and Resilience Education, the study revealed that there is significant difference in the level of DRRM compliance when respondents are grouped according to the type of school. This indicates that selected public schools in Tanay Sub-Office offering inclusive education programs have a higher level DRRM compliance on these CSS pillars. Furthermore, the study discovered that schools offering inclusive education programs were more effective in promoting school disaster management compared to regular high schools. However, in terms of safe learning facility, the study revealed that there is no significant difference between the schools offering inclusive education programs and regular schools. Further investigation is necessary to examine these deviations and ascertain optimal strategies for implementing DRRM in various educational settings.

Based on the results of the study, the following are hereby recommended: It is highly recommended for the Department of Education to revisit and update its Comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) policy and support framework, Comprehensive School Safety, to align with global standards and consider the needs of all learners.

It is recommended for schools to strengthen student-led school watching and hazard mapping to engage students in disaster preparedness and management. Moreover, establishing an Early Warning System (EWS) can help build safety awareness and foster a culture of safety. Schools should also remind class advisers to conduct debriefing sessions for students and provide basic psychological first aid. Schools should rebuild, restore, and repair affected buildings to increase resilience to hazard situations.

It is recommended for schools to allocate a budget for regular maintenance of school facilities and establish temporary learning spaces for disaster aftermath. Capacitating teachers and school personnel on DRRM measures tailored to their needs is further recommended.

It is recommended for education administrators to regularly review and update their DRRM plans, involve community stakeholders, and advocate for the inclusion of learners with special needs in DRRM activities.

Future research may consider investigating factors contributing to higher DRRM implementation in inclusive education programs and longitudinal studies to evaluate the long-term influence of DRRM programs on disaster preparedness and resilience..

References

- Abayao, L. (2020). Disaster risk governance in northern Philippine communities: Issues and prospects in climate change talks. In *Climate Change Governance in Asia* (pp. 232-255). Routledge.
- Alcayna, T., Bolletino, V., Dy, P., & Vinck, P. (2016). Resilience and Disaster Trends in the Philippines: Opportunities for National and Local Capacity Building. *PLOS*.
- Asian Development Bank (2013). *ADBI Working Paper Series Disaster Risk Management at the National Level* Asian Development Bank Institute.
- Asio, M., J. (2021, January 17). Disaster Awareness and Level of Compliance to Disaster Programs in a Highly Urbanized City. *Ssrn.com*.
- Baluran, G. (2023). The Level of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Program Implementation Among Public Elementary Schools: Basis for A Proposed "Our School, Our Safe Zone" Program. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 10(6).
- Bernardy, & Schmid. (2018). Ensuring Students Feel Safe at School. *ACSA Resource Hub* - . <https://content.acsa.org/ensuring-students->

feel-safe-at-school/

Boon, H. J., Brown, L. H., Tsey, K., Speare, R., Pagliano, P., Usher, K., & Clark, B. (2011). School Disaster Planning for Children with Disabilities: A Critical Review of the Literature. *International Journal of Special Education*, v26, p223-237.

Conde, A. E. (2020). Disaster Risk Reduction Management of University of Rizal System: Perspectives for Strategic Action. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(1), 279-290.

Cubillas, A. U., Aviles, G. M., & Cubillas, T. E. (2022). Awareness, compliance and implementation of disaster risk reduction and management in flood-prone public elementary schools in Butuan city, Philippines. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, 9(5), 156–171. <https://doi.org/10.15739/ijeprr.22.017>

Dela Cruz, D., & Ormilla, R. (2022). Disaster Risk Reduction Management Implementation in the Public Elementary Schools of the Department of Education, Philippines. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 4(2), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.18485/ijdrm.2022.4.2.1>

Department of Economic and Social Affairs (DESA). (n.d.). Disaster risk reduction. Retrieved from: <https://sdgs.un.org/topics/disaster-risk-reduction>

DepEd. (2015). DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2015 - Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Coordination and Information Management Protocol.

DepEd. (2015). DepEd Order No. 37 s. 2015. Comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) in Basic Education Framework.

Diaz-Vicario, A. (2017). Practices that promote comprehensive school safety. *New Trends and Issues Proceedings on Humanities and Social Sciences*. [Online]. 01, pp 304-312.

DIDRRN. (2018). Disability Inclusive Disaster Risk Management: Voices from the Field and Good Practices. Retrieved from http://www.didrrn.net/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/web_CBM_Disability_Inclusive_Disaster_Risk_Management.pdf

Domingo, S. N., & Manejar, A. J. A. (2018). Disaster preparedness and local governance in the Philippines (No. 2018-52). PIDS Discussion Paper Series.

Ecolin-Campilla, M. (2016). Disaster risk reduction management practices of school managers. In *Third Asia Pacific Conference on Advanced Research* (pp. 207-217).

ESCAP. (2015). Overview of Natural Disasters and their Impacts. UNESCAP.ORG.ESCAP, 2015

GAATES. (2013). GUIDELINE ON INCLUSIVE DISASTER RISK REDUCTION: Early Warnings and Accessible Broadcasting. Retrieved from http://www.old.gaates.org/resources-disaster/Early_Warning_and_Accessible_Broadcasting.pdf

Give2Asia. (2018). Facilitating Inclusion in Disaster Preparedness: A Practical Guide for CBOs, Philippines.

Global Disaster Preparedness Center (2023). Early Warning Systems. (2023, October 31). PrepareCenter.

Global Alliance for Disaster Risk Reduction and Resilience in the Basic Education Sector. (2022). Comprehensive School Safety Framework 2022-2030 for Child Rights and Resilience in the Education Sector. <https://inee.org/sites/default/files/resources/The-Comprehensive-School-Safety-Framework-2022-2030-for-Child-Rights-and-Resilience-in-the-Education-Sector.pdf>

Hadi, S. (2019). Learning from the legacy of post-disaster recovery in Indonesia for the acceleration of post-disaster recovery in Lombok. *Jurnal Perencanaan Pembangunan: The Indonesian Journal of Development Planning*, 3(1), 14-31.

Haug, P. (2017). Understanding inclusive education: ideals and reality. *Scandinavian Journal of Disability Research*, 19(3), 206–217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15017419.2016.1224778>

Heinemann, A. W., Feuerstein, M., Frontera, W. R., Gard, S. A., Kaminsky, L. A., Negrini, S., Lorie Gage Richards, & Vallée, C. (2020). Rehabilitation Is a Global Health Priority. *BMC Health Services Research*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-020-4962-8>

Johnson, V. A., Ronan, K. R., Johnston, D. M., & Peace, R. (2014). Evaluations of disaster education programs for children: A methodological review. *International journal of disaster risk reduction*, 9, 107-123.

Kingston, B., Sabrina Arredondo Mattson, Dymnicki, A., Spier, E., Fitzgerald, M., Shipman, K., Goodrum, S., Woodward, W., Witt, J., Hill, K. G., & Elliott, D. (2018). Building Schools' Readiness to Implement a Comprehensive Approach to School Safety. *Clinical Child and Family Psychology Review*, 21(4), 433–449. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10567-018-0264-7>

Lopez et. al. (2018) Level of Compliance with the Risk Reduction and Disaster Preparedness Program among Public Secondary Schools in Buenavista, Bohol, Philippines. (2018). ResearchGate. <https://doi.org/10.15631//aubgsp.v12i1.86>

- Mamon, M. A. C., Suba, R. A. V., & Son, I. L. (2017). Disaster risk reduction knowledge of Grade 11 students: Impact of senior high school disaster education in the Philippines. *International Journal of Health System and Disaster Management*, 5(3), 69.
- Mella, M. C. G., Martinez, M. Q., & Lisay, M. S. (2021). Capacity-building initiatives for a disaster-ready school community: development of a comprehensive disaster risk reduction management plan by. Copyright© 2021 by I DREAM Research Journal, 222.
- Tadashi Nakasu, & Chutaporn Amrapala. (2023). Evidence-based disaster risk assessment in Southeast Asian countries. *Natural Hazards Research*, 3(2), 295–304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nhres.2023.04.001>
- National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA). (2017). - CALABARZON Website, <https://calabarzon.neda.gov.ph/regional-profile/>
- Oro, N. B., & Benavides, N. G. (2020). Enhancement on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) operations of the schools in the 2 nd Congressional District of Sorsogon. *International Journal of Novel Research in Marketing Management and Economics* Vol. 7, Issue 2, pp: (77-82), Month: May - August 2020, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com
- Paci-Green, R., Varchetta, A., McFarlane, K., Iyer, P., & Goyeneche, M. (2020). Comprehensive school safety policy: A global baseline survey. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 44, 101399–101399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2019.101399>
- Pati, R. C., & Cruz, A. P. (2017). Flood vulnerability of the town of Tanay, Rizal, Philippines. *Philipp. J. Sci*, 146(2), 117-127.
- Punay, E. (2018). Kids with disabilities most vulnerable to disasters. *PhilStar*.
- Resilience Library. (2016). School Disaster Risk Management Guidelines for Southeast Asia | Rrcr-Resilience-Southeastasia.org. <https://www.rrcr-resilience-southeastasia.org/document/school-disaster-risk-management-guidelines-for-southeast-asia/>
- Robas, R.J. (2016). Flood disaster risk reduction and risk management of Pasig City. Retrieved from www.researchgate.net
- Ronan, K. R., Alisic, E., Towers, B., Johnson, V. A., & Johnston, D. M. (2015). Disaster preparedness for children and families: a critical review. *Current psychiatry reports*, 17, 1-9.
- Ronoh, S., Gaillard, J., & Marlowe, J. (2017). Children with Disabilities in Disability-Inclusive Disaster Risk Reduction: Focussing on School Settings. ERIC.
- Syahputri, D. M., Aris, Y., Hafida, S. H. N., Widiyatmoko, W., Anwar, Y., & Dewi, R. P. (2022). Implementation of comprehensive school safety: the risk reduction and resilience education pillar in State Senior High School 1 of Pacitan and Islamic State Senior High School 1 of Pacitan, Indonesia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 986(1), 012016. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/986/1/012016>
- Serafica, R. (2014). #ZeroCasualty: Don't forget PWDs, elderly. Manila, Philippines: Rappler.
- SEAMEO (2015). SEAMEO 7 Priority areas + Action Agenda 2016-2020. https://www.seameo.org/SEAMEOWeb2/images/stories/Publications/Centers_Pub/SEAMEO_Education_agenda/04%20SEAMEO%207%20Priority%20Areas%20Implementation%20by%20Centres.pdf
- Stough, L. M., & Kang, D. (2015). The Sendai framework for disaster risk reduction and persons with disabilities. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*, 6(2), 140-149.
- Suleymanov, F. (2015). Issues of Inclusive Education: Some Aspects to be Considered. Number 4 *Electronic Journal for Inclusive Education*, 3(4). <https://corescholar.libraries.wright.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1175&context=eje>
- Tilly, Krish, & Patrick. (n.d.). Perceptions of disaster resilience and preparedness in the Philippines. https://hhi.harvard.edu/sites/hwpi.harvard.edu/files/humanitarianinitiative/files/prc-phillippine-report-final_0.pdf
- Thapa, A., Cohen, J., Guffey, S., & Higgins-D'Alessandro, A. (2013). A review of school climate research. *Review of Educational Research*, 83(3), 357-385.
- Tizon, R., Mae, S., & Comighud, T. (2020). Implementation of the Public Schools' Disaster Risk Reduction Implementation of the Public Schools' Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program and Level of Capabilities to Respond Management Program and Level of Capabilities to Respond
- Valeria, M., Cabello., Karina, D., Véliz., Ana, M., Moncada-Arce., María, Irrázaval, García-Huidobro., Felipe, Juillerat. (2021). Disaster Risk Reduction Education: Tensions and Connections with Sustainable Development Goals. *Sustainability*, doi: 10.3390/SU131910933
- Villabon, A.R. (2020). Assessing The Level of Schools' Disaster Preparedness in The City Schools Division of Cabuyao. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*.
- Villamero, R. J. (2016, December 1). Retrieved August 1, 2018, from Global Observatory for Inclusion

UNICEF. (2011). Temporary learning spaces in emergency situations. Humanitarian Library. <https://www.humanitarianlibrary.org/resource/temporary-learning-spaces-emergency-situations>

Vulnerable Philippines – working towards climate adaptation. (2023, March 28). Preventionweb.net. <https://www.preventionweb.net/news/vulnerable-philippines-working-towards-climate-adaptation>

Wester, M. (2017). Disability Inclusive Disaster Risk Reduction: Practices of participation in Albay province, the Philippines. Disaster Studies International Development Studies Wageningen University & Research.

Widowati, Evi, Wahyudi Istiono, & Adi Heru Husodo. (2021). The development of Disaster Preparedness and Safety School model: A Confirmatory Factor Analysis. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 53, 102004–102004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.102004>

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